

FOCUS-5: The feasibility of RO-Crates as a standards-based framework for auditing federated analyses and projects

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1. Executive Project Summary

FOCUS-5 set out to develop the first standards-based framework for auditing federated analyses - where data from different physical locations is analysed. It is important that patients know that their data is handled responsibly and in line with legal and ethical standards during this type of analysis.

We specifically focussed on the application and enhancement of the **TREvolution Five Safes Research Object Crates (5SROC)** in the NHS England Secure Data Environment (SDE) network and within an SDE-DataSHIELD context – as a method to log where data comes from, where it goes, and how it is used when analysis occurs across multiple locations. We had further opportunity to explore the integration of these concepts with **K8TRE**, to help the provisioning of open-source federated analysis tools like DataSHIELD that are commonly used by researchers. We worked across DARE UK TRE adopter projects and the SDE network to develop clear and shared definitions of federated data and federated analysis that anyone can use, regardless of which technology or system they work with.

Significant outputs from FOCUS-5 include:

- The **first federated analysis within the SDE network** in August 2025. DataSHIELD was used to analyse synthetic data between Lancashire and South Cumbria SDE and Wessex SDE. This successfully demonstrated exploratory analytics and machine learning functionality with DataSHIELD.
- Several **software to help the adoption of the 5SROCs** including [rocrateR](#), [dsROCrates](#) and the [CR8TOR](#) suite of tools (full details on all tools in [Appendix 1](#)).
- **Comprehensive documentation and support for the installation** of these tools was tailored for the SDE network.
- **Collaborative public patient involvement and engagement (PPIE)** across DARE UK TRE adopter projects and the SDE network on several areas to develop shared language and communicate concepts around consent of data use, federated analytics, trust and transparency.

We have demonstrated that the TREvolution 5SROCs can be adopted within the SDE network and in federated analysis tools to expand transparency around where data comes from, how it is used within an SDE and how it is used safely during analysis of data from multiple locations using DataSHIELD. The FOCUS-5 project outputs help build public and domain trust in tools, systems and processes to support research with patient data across boundaries, including geographical, and enable the use of data that would typically be blocked due to patient privacy, the size of the data or commercial sensitivity. The impact FOCUS-5 supports:

- **Data custodians:** providing a choice of safe tools aligned to national standards and frameworks that can run together to enable safe research use of patient data within an SDE or as part of a research network that includes data from multiple locations.
- **Researchers:** familiar tools like DataSHIELD that are already used within international research networks are made available within the NHS SDE environment and can be adopted within TREs.
- **Industry:** familiar tools like DataSHIELD that are already used within trial networks are made available within the NHS SDE environment and can be adopted within TREs.
- **Patients and the public:** socially aligned, transparent tools aligned with common standards and demonstrable trust.

2. Overview of TRevolution Capabilities Utilised

In FOCUS-5 we worked with the Five Safes RO-Crate and K8TRE TRevolution capabilities.

2.1. Five Safes Research Object Crate (5SROC)

Research Objects (ROs) are machine readable mechanisms to communicate diverse digital and real-world resources relevant to research outputs. They provide structured archives of data and metadata, notes and slides, workflows, or analysis software. RO-Crate provides an integrated view of the RO to make the research findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR).

The Five Safes Research Object Crate (5SROC) was developed as an RO-Crate profile (<https://trefx.uk/5s-crate/0.4/>) as part of the DARE UK Phase 1 Driver Projects (TRE-FX). This provides a standardised method for documenting the history and movement of data and analysis within and across Trusted Research Environments (TREs) in line with the Five Safes Framework¹. As part of the TRE-FX driver project, the open-source federated analysis tool DataSHIELD was implemented as a proof-of-concept work.

The current 5SROC standard is not designed to define Secure Data Environment (SDE) infrastructure requirements for federated data projects represented within an RO-Crate. The following applications of RO-Crates had not been considered prior to FOCUS-5:

1. RO-Crates to support automated infrastructure provisioning for federated analysis.
2. RO-Crates for federated analysis auditing.

Furthermore, prior to this project there was no R package to interface with RO-Crates.

¹ Desai, T et al., 2016. Five Safes: designing data access for research, University of the West of England Bristol, Economics Working Paper Series 1601, p5. <https://www2.uwe.ac.uk/faculties/BBS/Documents/1601.pdf>

2.2. K8TRE

K8TRE is a cloud-agnostic, open-source, SATRE compliant TRE framework designed to address traditional TRE infrastructure complexity and deployment costs by leveraging modern microservice (i.e. Kubernetes) and CI/CD (ArgoCD) technologies (<https://docs.k8tre.org/latest/>). K8TRE offers a foundational reference implementation that is highly configurable to meet diverse organisational and disciplinary needs whilst lowering the barrier-to-entry for organisations seeking to utilise federated networks, including DataSHIELD. K8TRE enables efficient cross-sector collaboration on platform engineering through its modular, microservices-based architecture and ephemeral development environments. While in early development, K8TRE has been deployed and evaluated across multiple institutions on diverse organisation infrastructures including both in the Cloud and on-premises. Prior to FOCUS-5:

1. Third party open-source federation services could not be provisioned via K8TRE.
2. Capability to deploy common TRE components within different infrastructures via K8TRE had not been proven within the SDE network.
3. A cross-organisation test environment for investigating the applicability of the 5SROC profile within a federated SDE workflow using DataSHIELD/Opal did not exist.

3. Feedback on the Capabilities Adopted

3.1. Utility of Five Safes RO Crates in an SDE context

Orchestration of SDE infrastructure and data resources for federated research projects is a complex and manual-intensive practice, with fragmented processes for data governance, identity management, disclosure checks, and resource provisioning. RO-Crates, offer a potential lightweight approach for representing the metadata needed to drive the provisioning of infrastructure resources, represent provenance information and federated datasets as projects are initiated and traverse across organisational SDE boundaries.

We investigated the suitability of adopting the 5SROC Profile to represent new forms of metadata and workflow execution actions required to support semi-automated project governance, data ingress and dynamic resource provisioning to underpin cross-organisation federated DataSHIELD analysis. We could not represent everything we needed to by using the 5SROC profile alone, so we had to create a metamodel which encompassed it and other metadata models.

Leveraging K8TRE and the 5SROC Profile approach, we have deployed the CR8TOR framework (Figure 1) that addresses the challenge of federated data project orchestration across TREs by extending standardised metadata models (5SROC Profile) to take an active role

in creating project-dependent infrastructure alongside the representation of project governance metadata. CR8TOR comprises several components to demonstrate how contextual project information modelled in RO-Crate-like schemas can provide machine-readable representations of research resource requirements.

Figure 1 - CR8TOR Framework Architecture Design

By extending the Kubernetes API with custom resource definitions (CRDs), these resource descriptions sit alongside traditional research object metadata while maintaining FAIR principles and act as computable units that can be recreated as required. Moreover, CR8TOR supports automated data ingress from external sources, project governance controls, data provenance tracking, and on-demand reconciliation of project resources, including research workspaces, user accounts and network access policies. Deployed across cloud and on-premises infrastructure supporting multi-institution collaborations, the same declarative models can be shared across deployments, enabling reproducible and portable research settings.

By leveraging the utility of the 5SROC Profile approach, through FOCUS-5, we demonstrate how provisionable metadata may strengthen methodological foundations of federated research by allowing TRE infrastructure specifications—including workspace configuration, controlled access rules, and project-specific identities—to be described, shared, and reproduced with consistency and automation. CR8TOR ensures compliance with the 5-Safes framework through:

- Safe Projects: Structured project governance and approval workflows
- Safe People: Identity verification and role-based access control

- Safe Data: Metadata validation and secure data handling
- Safe Settings: Controlled research environments and access policies
- Safe Outputs: Audited data transfer with integrity verification

3.1.1. CR8TOR Metamodel

Figure 2 - CR8TOR Metamodel Schema

The CR8TOR metamodel provides a comprehensive schema definition for representing a K8TRE data project’s metadata to support automated data ingress, governance and resource deployment. Built using a Link Modelling Language (LinkML), the metamodel merges key entities from the 5SROC Profile with attributes from data model standards for cross-domain user management (i.e. SCIM) and infrastructure resource definitions in Kubernetes (i.e. OpenAPI Specification) while preserving formal linkage to the entities defined within each foundational model. Critically, the CR8TOR metamodel (developed as a Python module) along with supporting LinkML validation, code generation and data formatting tools provides a single source-of-truth data model that can be integrated into each CR8TOR component to ensure the consistency and integrity of a K8TRE data project’s metadata. For example, the CR8TOR Web UI uses the metamodel to generate dynamic UI forms (see below) while the CR8TOR CLI can consistently validate and populate custom resource definitions (CRDs) that describe project-dependent resources CR8TOR should provision in K8TRE.

The CR8TOR metamodel schema (Figure 2) developed as part of FOCUS-5 aims to model project metadata required to support project governance, data ingress and resource

deployment operations that make up the CR8TOR workflow. The CR8TOR metamodel module is described in detail at <https://github.com/karectl-crates/cr8tor-metamodel>.

3.1.2. CR8TOR tooling

3.1.2.1. CR8TOR CLI

The CR8TOR Command Line Interface (CLI) module provides a set of commands (Table 1) to manage the entire data project lifecycle extending the 5SROC Profile workflow, from project initiation to data publication into a K8TRE workspace. The CLI module can be run from the terminal by an administrator or integrated in an application (e.g. CR8TOR Web UI & Workflow Executor GitHub Action) as a Python module to perform operations on the K8TRE project to complete the CR8TOR workflow (outlined above).

Table 1 - CR8TOR CLI operations, full technical documentation <https://lsc-sde-crates.github.io/cr8tor/cr8tor-cli/commands/>

Operation	Description
Initiate	creates a CR8TOR project and raises a pull request (PR) for a TRE administrator to review in the specified GitHub CR8TOR projects repository. An initiated project bundle includes mandatory metadata YAML files validated against the CR8TOR metamodel. In addition, initiate configures security groups and write protections on a project's directory in the CR8TOR projects repository.
Create	generates an initial RO-Crate representation of the CR8TOR project bundle as a non-serialised BagIt artefact within the CR8TOR project bundle. In addition, the command generates a UUID for the CR8TOR project.
Validate	performs semantic validation functions on a project's data ingress and governance metadata. This includes validity checks on connection details to the specified data source (e.g. PostgreSQL) from the target K8TRE cluster via the CR8TOR Publisher Service (see below). In addition, the requested data schema (i.e. table/column naming and data types) are confirmed to ensure downstream data transfer phases can execute successfully.
Deploy	creates and stores custom resource definitions based on project deployment and governance metadata that the CR8TOR Operator (see below) uses to automatically reconcile required project infrastructure resources (e.g. user accounts, applications).
Sign Off	represents the action of approving a project for staging the requested data and infrastructure resources into the target TRE. For example, when the command is triggered via the GitHub workflow, the workflow is paused until an authorised administrator reviews the CR8TOR project provenance information in the bundle and confirms its release via the GitHub Actions management UI.
Stage Transfer	moves data from the external data source to target sink within the target TRE. CR8TOR projects support a series of sink types including file storage (e.g. Azure Storage Account) and database (e.g. PostgreSQL) endpoints.

Disclosure	represents a final human-in-the-loop step to verify that all data/infrastructure resources to be made available via the CR8TOR project are correct, along with all action provenance information included in the project bundle.
Publish	transfer requested data and infrastructure resources from staging to production, ensuring data and resources are accessible to the requesting users. The publish command communicates with CR8TOR TRE services and controllers (i.e. Publisher, Operator) to facilitate user access and resource availability.

3.1.2.2. CR8TOR Web UI

Figure 3 - Web UI Project Creation Form

CR8TOR Web user interface (UI) provides a web application comprising a front-end (Figure 3) and REST API to initiate a CR8TOR project. Distributed as a single Docker image (<https://ghcr.io/karectl-crates/cr8tor-webui/cr8tor-webui:latest>), the application allows K8TRE operators to populate and submit CR8TOR projects to an enterprise's target CR8TOR projects repository in GitHub. The application is a standalone web app that can be run locally using Docker Desktop.

The frontend generates a dynamic UI form wizard based on CR8TOR's metamodel to capture contextual information that the CR8TOR framework requires to facilitate governance checks, semi-automated data ingestion and TRE resource provisioning (see <https://github.com/karectl-crates/cr8tor-webui> for more information).

3.1.2.3. CR8TOR Operator

The CR8TOR Operator is a Kubernetes-native operator that translates the 5SROC project metadata into live infrastructure within K8TRE. Deployed as a Kubernetes workload, it registers and manages Custom Resource Definitions (CRDs) generated from the CR8TOR Metamodel. These CRDs represent the project entities (workspaces, identities, access policies, and network configurations) in a Kubernetes-native, GitOps compatible way.

The Operator implements a plugin architecture through a plugin registry, enabling extensibility without modifying the core operator loop. Together, a series of plugins drive the key K8TRE capabilities for each project: multi-tenant namespace isolation, network policy enforcement, project-scoped storage allocation, and OAuth client provisioning, all reconciled against the project's approved governance metadata.

Without the CR8TOR Operator, TRE infrastructure provisioning would revert to manual, error-prone processes inconsistent with Five-Safes governance principles. It ensures no resource is created or modified outside a validated governance cycle. All changes are version-controlled via GitOps (ArgoCD), providing a full audit trail across FOCUS-5 partner sites and consistent, reproducible deployments in multi-institution federated environments.

3.1.2.4. *CR8TOR Publisher Service*

The CR8TOR Publisher service was developed to support validation and data movement phases of the CR8TOR workflow, that extends the 5SROC profile execution process. As a containerised web service deployable as a part of the K8TRE CR8TOR application set, it serves secure data access requests, enabling administrators via the CR8TOR CLI (see above) to request, approve, and retrieve datasets safely and efficiently from external data sources into target data storage locations (i.e. file storage, DBMS) within K8TRE. CR8TOR Publisher represents a FastAPI-based REST API microservice that supports: data extraction from source databases (e.g. SQL Server, MySQL, PostgreSQL, Databricks); dynamic data packaging and format conversion based on a CR8TOR project's data request schema and data staging and production management within a K8TRE cluster. Further technical details: <https://lsc-sde-crates.github.io/cr8tor/cr8tor-publisher/overview/>.

3.1.3. **Opal**

To align with K8TRE, Opal (a key component of the DataSHIELD software stack) was improved so it can be deployed natively on Kubernetes clusters, enabling administrators to better manage system resources and scale analysis workloads as needed. This was released in Opal v5.2 (<https://www.obiba.org/pages/news/release/opal/5.2/>).

3.2. Utility of Five Safes RO Crates in a DataSHIELD-SDE context

3.2.1. DataSHIELD overview

DataSHIELD (datashield.org) is a well-established federated analysis framework enacted in a series of open-source software and has been used for federated analysis internationally for over 13 years. It uses a client-server architecture to enable analysis without viewing the raw data or sharing individual level information. Only summary-level statistics leave the data controller environment and return to the analyst in real-time after data privacy thresholds - including automated statistical disclosure checks - are satisfied. The types of allowable privacy thresholds are set by the data controller. This privacy-by-design architecture aligns with the Five Safes Framework (see Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Schematic DataSHIELD workflow diagram of DataSHIELD²

DataSHIELD is designed to work natively in a federated manner, allowing an analyst to run analyses across multiple remote data sets simultaneously without the data being moved or shared². Unique to DataSHIELD, its functions have been designed from statistical first principles to create analysis outputs based on the individual level data at multiple locations equivalent to if all the data from each site had been moved into one central location^{3,4}. This contrasts with carrying out aggregated single-location outputs (study-level), the approach of most federated analysis tools.

The aim of this work was to adopt the 5SROC infrastructure within DataSHIELD, enabling a flexible framework for auditing federated analyses. To achieve this, we developed a two-level architecture: one component integrates with DataSHIELD to generate an RO-Crate, while the

² Avraam et al., (2025). DataSHIELD: mitigating disclosure risk in a multi-site federated analysis platform, *Bioinformatics Advances*, Volume 5, Issue 1, 2025, vbaf046, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioadv/vbaf046>

³ Jones et al., (2012). DataSHIELD – shared individual-level analysis without sharing the data. <https://doi.org/10.5324/nje.v21i2.1499>

⁴ Jones et al., (2013). Combined analysis of correlated data when data cannot be pooled. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sta4.19>

second component parses the RO-Crate to construct an audit (Figure 5). This infrastructure is designed to support extensibility, allowing other federated analysis tools to be easily incorporated, provided they can export information compliant with the 5SROC specification.

As the core DataSHIELD packages are primarily implemented in R, and no suitable R interface for RO-Crates was available at the outset of the project, we developed a dedicated R package *rocrateR* to address this gap ([Appendix 1](#)).

Figure 5 -Single node RO-Crate workflow with dsROCrates

3.2.2. Mapping DataSHIELD concepts to the Five Safes RO-Crates

The current version of the 5SROC profile (v0.4 - <https://trefx.uk/5s-crate/0.4>) assumes a discrete, predefined workflow execution model with explicit *CreateAction* (<https://schema.org/CreateAction>) declared inputs, workflow artefacts and formalised outputs. DataSHIELD, however, operates as an interactive, session-based federated analysis environment, where analysts issue incremental commands against pre-hosted datasets and no formal workflow object, run request or ingestible inputs exist.

This mismatch meant that mandatory profile components such as referencing a Workflow Crate, specifying workflow inputs/outputs and modelling a single executable action cannot be completely represented from DataSHIELD concepts. Moreover, our approach was one of retrospective logs and server settings being extracted, which does not satisfy the prospective workflow semantics expected by the profile. In addition to this, DataSHIELD backends typically expose limited identity and governance metadata and outputs are disclosure-controlled summaries rather than exportable artefacts, meaning key sections of the profile (inputs, outputs, requested workflow run, etc.) are either inapplicable or only partially implementable. We did extend one of the back ends (Opal) to enhance the user information it collects when authentication is performed via OpenID Connect to address some of this.

We mapped the concepts across the DataSHIELD ecosystem to the 5SROC (<https://github.com/FederatedMethods/five-safes-mapping>) summarised in Table 2. The 5SROC profile specifies items that either *must* or *should* be present, but it does not explicitly align them to five safes categories. We aligned them to the five safes categories in our

dsROCrate package (<https://github.com/FederatedMethods/dsROCrate>) to give additional semantic meaning.

Table 2 - Mappings of DataSHIELD ecosystem packages (rocrateR & dsROCrate) to 5SROC profile.

dsROCrate / rocrateR Function	5s-crate Section	Conformance Status	Notes
rocrateR::rocrate_5s()	Profile Conformance	✔ Full	Correct profile declaration and metadata structure
dsROCrate::safe_data()	Inputs	⚠ Partial	Captures referenced study tables; not workflow inputs
dsROCrate::safe_project()	Responsible Project	⚠ Partial	Project entity created; not linked via sourceOrganization as required
dsROCrate::safe_people()	Requesting Agent	⚠ Partial	Person entity created; limited backend metadata
dsROCrate::safe_setting()	Inputs / Safe Settings	⚠ Contextual	Captures server config & privacy filters; not workflow parameters
dsROCrate::safe_output()	Referencing Workflow Crate / Outputs	✘ Structural mismatch	Logs captured; no workflow crate or formal CreateAction
rocrateR::bag_rocrate()	Archive Serialisation	✔ Full	BagIt ZIP compliant packaging
—	Requested Workflow Run	✘ Not implemented	No formal CreateAction with workflow instrument
—	Review Process	✘ Not implemented	Governance lifecycle external to crate

3.2.3. Audit tool

Figure 6 - Summary diagram of a sample audit report generated with dsROCrate on a single node.

Using the mappings to the 5SROC profile, we were able to automatically build audit reports which included sections on each of the five safes and how they were being met, for example, information about the DataSHIELD environment (installed packages, disclosure control settings, etc.) was presented in the safe setting part of the audit report. To give a simple overview of the audit, a summary diagram is automatically generated, as in Figure 6.

3.2.3.1. Multi node Five Safes RO-Crates audit

Figure 7 - Multi node RO-Crate workflow with dsROCrates.

By aligning on the RO-Crate format it means we were able to process information from multiple nodes into a single audit report, giving a federated network overview of what is happening (see Figure 7 and Figure 8).

Figure 8 - Summary diagram of a sample audit report generated with dsROCrates on multiple nodes.

A set of three different personas were defined for the audit reports, with each generating a customised report:

1. **A data controller auditing a person** (or people) within a project to see everything they have access to and have done on a single node.
2. **A data controller auditing a project** to see everyone who has access and what they have done on a single node.

3. A consortium manager auditing who has access to what and what they have done over a distributed network of multiple nodes.

This allowed a simplified mechanism of invoking the various sub-commands to collate and present the data.

3.2.4. DataSHIELD adaptations for SDE Deployment

The processes and operational aspects required by NHS SDEs to deploy and support DataSHIELD for federated analysis were explored and three areas were addressed:

- **Infrastructure adaptations:** Opal required extension to include native support for Microsoft SQL Server as a database backend, making it easier to integrate with data platforms commonly used in NHS organisations. (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/odbc.resourcer/index.html>).
- **CRAN installation:** consultation with SDE stakeholders identified a preference to install DataSHIELD's analysis packages directly from the CRAN (Comprehensive R Archive Network), as evidence that certain software quality thresholds have been achieved. Both dsBaseClient and dsBase packages are now included in the CRAN.
- **Human readable test outputs:** although DataSHIELD has extensive test suites, only technical logs were generated. We improved the readability with the development of a *Test Status Dashboard* (<https://federatedmethods.github.io/testsDashboard/>).

3.3. Feedback On Use of 5SROC Profile for SDE Project Governance and DataSHIELD contexts

To test the adoptability of the extended 5SROC, we deployed K8TRE including CR8TOR and DataSHIELD over two phases into two NHS environments – Lancashire and South Cumbria (LSC) SDE and Wessex SDE. This offered an opportunity for each SDE to work through deployment documentation and operational considerations.

Phase 1: LSC had the full K8TRE stack deployed in their cloud provider, and Wessex installed DataSHIELD as a stand-alone service on premises. This enabled the first (to our knowledge) federated analysis between two SDEs in August 2025. We implemented a federated analysis of synthetic data using DataSHIELD's base functions and its machine learning functions.

Phase 2: Wessex SDE deployed the full K8TRE stack including CR8TOR and DataSHIELD within an on-premises environment. A project was successfully defined using the extended metadata model utilising 5SROC enabling evaluation of CR8TOR from three stakeholder perspectives: TRE operators, data engineers/governance specialists and data scientists performing federated queries via a DataSHIELD-ready TRE workspace. The Phase 1 analysis

was replicated using DataSHIELD client/server analysis packages. All components functioned successfully, with DataSHIELD capabilities handled via a dedicated 'dsUser' Opal account configured as the sole interface for DataSHIELD activity. This approach enables scalable shared use through separation and containment of permissions, enhanced security through multi-factor authentication and customisation of Opal's user management settings.

This phase proved the feasibility of adopting RO-Crates in SDEs. K8TRE provided Wessex and LSC SDEs with a cost-effective, standardised TRE environment to support the development, deployment, and testing of CR8TOR, enabling semi-automated provisioning and governance of resources for federated projects using DataSHIELD.

3.4. Overall Drawbacks and Recommendations for Improvement

As outlined above, the biggest hurdle was the assumption in the 5SROC profile definition that analysis would only be run as a workflow, which is counter to how DataSHIELD and some other distributed analytic tools operate. In the context of CR8TOR, the 5SROC model did not accommodate all required metadata, and additional data model standards were utilised alongside this. We did consider proposing a new ROC profile to meet our needs, but within the context of DataSHIELD, we decided to be non-compliant with the full 5SROC profile in the interim until the next version is developed, which should meet our needs.

3.5. Impact of Using the TRevolution Capabilities

K8TRE and the 5SROC specification have supported the delivery of new governance and resource deployment workflows that enhance the security and efficiency of configuring, operating and auditing federated data projects and federated analysis within and across TRE and SDE infrastructure.

3.6. Public Patient Involvement and Engagement

3.6.1. Approach

The project employed a multi-layered, collaborative methodology to bridge the gap between technical execution and public perception of concepts relating to federated analysis. Rather than working in isolation, PPIE (Public Patient Involvement and Engagement) professionals from **DARE UK TRE Early Adopters**, **NHS SDE (Secure Data Environment) PPIE Network**, and **PEDRI** formed an informal coalition. This "federated" approach to engagement pooled expertise from local ICB levels to national communities of practice. Areas of work FOCUS-5 led:

- **Stakeholder Consultation:** A language survey was developed with and circulated via members of the DARE UK Federated Analytics Community Interest Group and wider

network colleagues. This was in response to an increasingly recognised need to gather views in a structured way. This followed repeated informal discussions across multiple networks that highlighted variation in how governance, technical, policy, and public groups understand concepts such as “federation”

- **Co-production of communication tools using FAIR principles:** Working with the Federated Research Community Interest Group and Public Members have prototyped an interactive web map to host definitions and vocabularies that are themselves Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (<https://fa-ontology-mapping-rh44.vercel.app/>). This is part of a wider body of work that has identified the need to produce plain-English definitions as well as multimedia resources (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19368599>)
- **Public Involvement Strategy:** Engaging diverse groups, including the Lancashire and South Cumbria Public Advisory Group through iterative regular feedback sessions. A deliberate effort was made to include "non-expert" lay members to ensure resources remained accessible to those outside the data research bubble.

3.6.2. Findings

The exploration of terminology and efforts to translate them into relatable analogy and plain English revealed a significant "clarity gap" that complicates both internal operations and external trust. This impacts the creation of non-technical resources explaining concepts due to definitions drifting. Whilst generalisable definitions are less useful operatively and in specific contexts such as delivering a NHS SDE service, moving goal posts can create confusion not only for the public but also technical professional and collaborators. Definition inconsistencies existed, such as limited agreement on the term “federation,” and interpretations varying according to context. In particular, a distinction emerges between governance-oriented federation (policy-based collaboration) and mathematical or computational federation (relating to the execution of algorithms). This divergence contributes to ambiguity across stakeholder groups. Additionally, professional silos were observed to influence conceptual understanding and implementation approaches. Technical stakeholders, in some instances, default to models of data pooling, which may overlook or underrepresent the governance and privacy advantages associated with genuinely federated (non-pooled) methodologies. The language survey aims to provide more detail on these observations.

Insights from public participants revealed a pragmatic perspective. While there is general support for the societal benefits associated with data-driven discovery and knowledge

generation, this support is dependant upon robust privacy safeguards and clear assurances of confidentiality. Long-term PPIE members noted a shift in narrative. The original principle of "data access, not data sharing" is being challenged by increasing assumptions that data using some federated approaches may be shared across SDEs, even if within a federated network. This distinction is an area worth exploration with the public and their expectations. However, this perception does not align with certain implementations, such as DataSHIELD, in which only disclosure-controlled summary statistics—subject to governance-defined privacy settings—are permitted to leave the local environment.

3.6.3. Impact

The project has moved beyond theory into the creation of tangible infrastructure for future engagement. Impacts include:

- **Development of a Federated Analytics Language Tree/Taxonomy:** to facilitate professional and public stakeholder understanding of terms used in the domain. This may also act as a stable source of terminology to build out multi-media resources to improve access and visibility of content being created to support the mission of public understanding.
- A **suite of "agnostic" videos** that any researcher can use to explain data capture for protected characteristics.
- **Increased Convergence:** The formation of the **Federated Research Community Interest Group** has provided a central point for PPIE and communications professionals to communicate their messaging across DARE, HDR UK, and NHS SDEs.
- **Informed Policy Potential:** By identifying that even professionals struggle with these concepts, the project has slowed the "rush to communicate," ensuring that future public-facing policies are built on a foundation of professional consensus rather than fragmented definitions.

3.6.4. Challenges & Lessons Learned

The primary takeaway from these activities is that the scale of the communication challenge was initially underestimated, impacting the original PPIE plan in FOCUS-5 and necessitating a collaborative PPIE model. More effort needs to be made to better track inputs, accurately attribute and share credit to participants and organisations. This is because PPIE is a deeply

relational discipline and ensuring trust through more candid attribution would benefit not only it, but all research practices, with trust between in-groups linked to trust between out-groups⁵.

A key lesson concerns the tension between complexity and clarity. The risk of embedding fragmented, poorly aligned definitions is high. If definitions only serve short-term technical needs, they will not be resilient against future AI and privacy threats. Similarly, unilateral production of resources without broad consensus risks creating further confusion. The project learned to "cast the net wider," even if it slowed the timeline, to avoid excluding key professional or public perspectives.

FOCUS-5 highlighted the "expert lay" bias - where public advisory groups become increasingly familiar with the health data research environment potentially reducing their representativeness of the broader public. There is a need to periodically refresh public group membership to maintain genuine public perspectives.

Effective transparency was recognised as a form of infrastructure rather than a discrete output. True transparency requires more than glossaries; it requires a roadmap that openly acknowledges tensions between current deliverable technology and longer-term aspirations. Finally, accessibility emerged as a core consideration with a necessity for future resources to incorporate sign language overlays, audio descriptions, and "easy read" formats to ensure inclusivity across diverse audiences. However, such investment would only be prudent once a stable set of agreed and widely adopted definitions has taken hold.

4. Feedback on the Adoption Process

4.1. Challenges Encountered and How These Were Identified

At the start of the FOCUS-5 project, the broader TRevolution programme plan was still under development and had not yet been made publicly available. As a result, it was not possible to align the FOCUS-5 project proposal or implementation strategy with relevant components of the programme at an early stage.

The nature of participation as an early adopter introduced additional challenges. The K8TRE platform was not production-ready at the start of the project, and the Five Safes RO-Crate (5SROC) profile did not fully meet project requirements. These limitations constrained aspects of the implementation requiring certain compromises in technical development, including the inability to achieve full alignment with the 5SROC profile.

⁵ Nienaber A-MI, Woodcock A and Liotopoulos FK (2021) Sharing Data - Not With Us! Distrust as Decisive Obstacle for Public Authorities to Benefit From Sharing Economy. *Front. Psychol.* 11:576070. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.576070

These challenges provided an opportunity to contribute directly to the evolution of the underlying TRevolution capabilities. Feedback generated through this project informed development of both K8TRE and the next iteration of the 5SROC profile. The work presented in this report is likely to demonstrate stronger alignment with the evolving TRevolution stack than would have been achieved through the later adoption of fully matured capabilities.

The lack of an R package to interface with RO-Crates was unexpected, meaning we had to divert resources to develop this at an early stage of the project.

4.2. Recommendations for Improving the Adoption Process

Onboarding processes, training provision, and associated documentation have improved substantially since the start of the DARE UK Early Adopter projects, highlighting the importance of iterative feedback generated through these initiatives. Despite these advances, the long-term support model within TRevolution remains insufficiently defined, indicating a need for greater clarity on sustainability and ongoing operational support for new adopters.

4.3. Lessons Learned

The current implementation of the Five Safes RO-Crate (5SROC) profile is closely aligned with a workflow-oriented methodology. This means metadata generated by certain federated analysis platforms, such as DataSHIELD, may not conform strictly to this structure, highlighting a limitation in ROCs applicability across analytical environments.

Public and Patient Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) activities further reinforced a previously anticipated requirement: the need for a dedicated dashboard to support data controllers. Feedback indicated particular concern regarding a perceived shift in the data governance narrative—from Trusted Research Environments (TREs) or Secure Data Environments (SDEs) maintaining control over data, to scenarios implying the movement of data between environments. This highlights the importance of federated approaches, such as DataSHIELD, that enable analysis without necessitating data transfer.

5. 5. Conclusions and Future Direction

5.1 Conclusions

We have proven the feasibility of adopting RO-Crates within the SDE network and how it can serve as a foundation for a standards-based federated analysis auditing framework to expand transparency around where data comes from and how it is used within an SDE. Beyond this, we have demonstrated how RO-Crates - in combination with other metadata frameworks - can be

used to define and semi-automate the construction of end-to-end trusted research environments, including all resources necessary for a given project.

In both applications, however, the 5SROC profile proved insufficient to fully capture the processes involved. Specifically, in the context of CR8TOR, the model did not accommodate all required metadata, and for the federated auditing framework, the set of mandatory fields was overly restrictive. The FOCUS-5 project outputs help build public and domain trust in tools, systems and processes to support research with patient data across traditional boundaries, including geographical, and enable the use of data that would typically be blocked due to patient privacy, the size of the data or commercial sensitivity.

5.2 Future Use of TRevolution Capabilities

CR8TOR is already compatible with K8TRE to provide a standardised TRE environment enabling the semi-automated provisioning and Five Safes aligned governance of resources for federated projects. We will continue to advance the federated analysis auditing framework developed in this project, with the expectation that it will become an integral standard of the broader DataSHIELD ecosystem and adopted internationally. We have secured a DARE Catalyst grant (GROVE – <https://dareuk.org.uk/how-we-work/ongoing-activities/dare-uk-next-gen-catalysts/grove/>), through which we will extend the RO-Crates based federated analysis auditing framework to environmental data usage contexts.

5.3 Support Needed for Continued or Expanded Use

We require continued engagement with the RO-Crates team, and further development/ evolution of the Five Safes RO-Crates profile so that it can be adopted with utility beyond a workflow-based scenario.

6. Acknowledgements

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7. Appendix 1: Software outputs

Title	Description	Link
rocrateR	R package interface with RO-Crates	https://github.com/ResearchObject/ro-crate-r https://cran.r-project.org/package=rocrateR

dsROCRate	R package to RO-crate DataSHIELD analysis	https://github.com/FederatedMethods/dsROCRate
Opal v5.2	K8S support	https://github.com/obiba/opal/releases/tag/5.2.0
Opal v5.3	MSSQL support	https://github.com/obiba/opal/releases/tag/5.3.0
Opal v5.5	OpenID Connect support	https://github.com/obiba/opal/releases/tag/5.5.0
	Software	https://github.com/obiba/rock/releases
	Chart	https://github.com/obiba/helm-charts/releases
	Software	https://github.com/obiba/resourcer/releases
	Software	https://github.com/obiba/odbc.resourcer/releases https://cran.r-project.org/package=odbc.resourcer
dsBase & dsBaseClient	v6.3.4 Core DataSHIELD packages in CRAN	https://github.com/datashield/dsBase/releases/tag/6.3.4 https://github.com/datashield/dsBaseClient/releases/tag/6.3.4
	V6.3.5 Core DataSHIELD packages in the CRAN.	https://github.com/datashield/dsBase/releases/tag/6.3.5 https://github.com/datashield/dsBaseClient/releases/tag/6.3.5
Tests	DataSHIELD tests	https://github.com/FederatedMethods/testsDashboard
CR8TOR	Operator	https://github.com/karectl-crates/cr8tor
	Template	https://github.com/karectl-crates/cr8-cookiecutter
	Projects Repository Template	https://github.com/karectl-crates/cr8tor-projects
	Metamodel	https://github.com/karectl-crates/cr8tor-metamodel
	Publisher Microservice	https://github.com/lsc-sde-crates/cr8tor-publisher
	Documentation	https://github.com/karectl-crates/cr8tor/blob/docs/mph-tre-operator-guide/docs/operator-guide/overview.md

8. Appendix 2: PPIE outputs

Type	Description
Video resource	To support standardised PPIE metadata capture and improved informed consent processes for developing transparency infrastructure. Pre-Production animation 10.5281/zenodo.19369059 . Consent Animation Report 10.5281/zenodo.19368929
Infrastructure and tooling development	FOCUS-5 has led the initiation of a patient, public engagement and insight dashboard for the SDE programme through a collaboration with NHS SDE PPIE community, PANORAMA early adopter project with additional funding support from NHS Transform. 10.5281/zenodo.19369306
PPPIE professionals Network consolidation	Contributing to the DARE UK Federated Research Community Interest Group supporting and strengthening collaboration across PPIE, communications and technical stakeholders spanning DARE early adopters, PEDRI and NHS SDE regions. Developed the strategy to support communication and alignment internally, towards robust co-produced resources that span multiple stakeholders
Federation Language Community Survey	Led the development of the Federated Data: Technical Definitions survey with input from the Dare UK Federated Research Community Interest Group to explore language and map current landscape
Federation Language community map	Under development – a web accessible, searchable interactive map of common terms used in federation. Demo: https://fa-ontology-mapping-rh44.vercel.app/ . Report: 10.5281/zenodo.19368599